

MANUAL FOR THE LUNEBURG STEWARDSHIP PROGRAMME

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Table of Contents

	Page
1. Key Grass Species Technique	3
2. Method for determining the key grass species for Luneburg	5
3. Assessment of Veld Condition	7
4. Point Quadrat Surveys	7
5. The Disc Pasture Meter	8
6. Key Grass Species Assessment Form	12
7. Glossary & Interpretation of Veld Condition Surveys	15

1. The Key Grass Species Technique

The assessment of range or veld condition provides the means of tracking trends in the condition of the veld involving either an improvement or degradation, and to formulate veld management practices for livestock farming or wild life systems. This can be a daunting and difficult task for the farmer/game manager as a wide knowledge of grass species and their identification is required. The Key Grass Species technique was developed by Professor Winston Trollope to assist veld managers with the assessment of veld condition. It was designed to be simple, practical and effective and encompasses the basic knowledge of grasses that most farmers already possess. Instead of having to identify all the grass species in order to follow trends brought about by management practices, the land user now only has to identify the few key grass species that are indicators of good or poor management practices.

Veld condition refers to the condition of the vegetation in relation to some functional characteristic/s (Trollope, *et.al.*, 1990) and in the case of livestock production based on grassland vegetation comprises the potential of the grass sward to produce forage for grazers, grass fuel to support controlled burns and its resistance to accelerated soil erosion as influenced by the basal and aerial cover of the grass sward.

The following procedure was used for developing the key grass species technique for assessing veld condition:

Step 1: Identify and list all the grass species occurring in the study area noting their identification characteristics for use in the field.

Step 2: Based on careful observations in the field and consultations with local land users, subjectively classify all the known grass species in the area into Decreaser and Increaser species according to their reaction to a grazing gradient i.e. from high to low grazing intensities as follows:

DECREASER SPECIES: Grass & herbaceous species that decrease when veld is under or over grazed;

INCREASER I SPECIES: Grass & herbaceous species that increase when veld is under grazed or selectively grazed;

INCREASER II SPECIES: Grass & herbaceous species that increase when veld is over grazed.

Step 3: Based on experience, observation and local knowledge subjectively allocate forage and fuel factors on a scale of 0 - 10 according to the potential of the different grass species to produce forage for bulk grazers like cattle and fuel for supporting a surface fire. This procedure is used because it conforms to the concept of veld condition being the condition of the vegetation in relation to some functional characteristics and in this case the potential to produce grass forage and grass fuel.

Step 4: Using the information from Step 3, develop a technique for assessing the condition of the grass sward based on the classification of the grass species into Decreaser and Increaser species together with their respective forage and fuel factors.

Step 5: Conduct grass surveys over the widest range of grassland, in as many different conditions as possible, and with these data statistically identify the key grass species that have the greatest positive and negative effect on veld condition in terms of their potential for producing forage. The potential for producing forage is calculated for each grass survey by multiplying the respective forage factors with the percentage relative frequency for each of the herbaceous plant species recorded during the different grass surveys. The sum of these products is expressed as the forage score for each sample site. The selection of the key grass species is done using a multiple regression analysis where the forage score is the dependent variable and the percentage frequency for each recorded grass or herbaceous species is the independent variable. The resultant regression model is then used for estimating the forage production potential of the veld at any sample site. Fuel scores are calculated in the same manner and are used in a multiple regression analysis for developing the regression model for estimating the fuel production potential of the veld at any sample site. The resultant regression models are tested statistically using data from additional independent grass surveys where the relationship between the predicted and observed forage and fuel scores is determined and statistically evaluated. Finally the data from the independent grass surveys are used to subjectively evaluate the outputs of the simplified key grass species technique for assessing veld condition according to the experience of local land owners.

The reason for selecting the key grass species in terms of their forage production potential is because the major portion of the Luneberg area is used for livestock production and it is therefore essential that the key grass species be selected to reflect the grazing potential of the area. Experience has indicated that key forage species are also capable of reflecting the potential of other functional characteristics like grass fuel potential that involve some aspect of plant production.

Data collection for the above steps is relatively simple and easily recorded in the field.

2. Method for determining the key grass species for Luneburg

The formulation of the Veld Management Program for the Luneburg Agriculture and Conservation Demonstration Project was conducted using the following steps:

Step 1: Identified the veld types in the project area according to Acocks (1988) Veld Types Map:
Acocks, J.P.H, 1988. Veld types of South Africa. *Mem. Bot. Surv. S. Afr.* No. 57. Botanical Research Institute, Dept. Agric & Water Supply, South Africa.

Step 2; Identified Homogeneous Vegetation Units (HVU's) within each veld type making use of the recently published information on the vegetation of South Africa by:

Mucina, L., Rutherford, M. & Powrie, L.W., 2005. Vegetation of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland. SANBI, Pretoria, 0001.

Step 3: Assessed the condition of the veld in each of the HVU's according to the procedure described by Trollope (1990): Trollope, W S W., 1990. Development of a technique for assessing veld condition in the Kruger National Park. *J. Grassld. Soc. South. Afr.*7, 1:46-51.

This involved conducting a full species assessment of the botanical composition of the grass sward together with recording the basal cover represented by the point to tuft distance developed by Hardy & Tainton (1993):

Hardy, M.B & Tainton, N.M., 1993. Towards a technique for determining basal cover in tufted grasslands. *Afr. J. Range & For. Sci* 10(2): 77-81.

Step 4: Using the full species data recorded during the assessment of the condition of the veld in the different HVU's developed a Key Species Technique for assessing veld condition using the procedure developed and described by Trollope (1990) in the Kruger National Park: Trollope, W S W., 1990. Development of a technique for assessing veld condition in the Kruger National Park. *J. Grassld. Soc. South. Afr.*7, 1:46-51.

The resultant simplified technique will apply to all the veld types occurring in the LUNEBURG AGRICULTURE AND CONSERVATION DEMONSTRATION PROJECT area.

Step 5: Based on the aforementioned assessment of the condition of the veld in the different HVU's formulate a veld management program comprising the most ecologically and economically appropriate Veld Management Practices, Systems and Layouts. The Veld Management Practices will include:

- Stocking rates;
- Grazing management;
- Rotational resting;
- Livestock ratios for cattle and sheep;
- Prescribed burning.

Farmers wishing to establish the correct Veld Management Practices can be assisted by consulting the following literature sources:

1. *Veld and Pasture Management in South Africa, 1981.* (ed) N.M. Tainton. Shuter & Shooter, Pietermaritzburg. 251-261.
2. *Veld Management in the Eastern Cape, 1989.* (eds) J E Danckwerts & W R Teague. Govt. Printer, Pretoria.
3. Trollope, W.S.W., 1992. Chapter 3: Veld management in grassland and savanna areas. In: *Guide to grasses of South Africa.* (ed). F.P. van Oudtshoorn. Briza Publications, Arcadia, Pretoria: 45-56.
4. *Veld Management In South Africa, 1999.* (ed). N.M. Tainton. University Natal Press, Pietermaritzburg. 412 - 422.

An example of a Veld Condition Assessment Form based on the above steps will be found in Section 6.

3. Assessment of Veld Condition

When conducting veld condition assessments the area under consideration should first be divided into homogeneous vegetation units i.e. areas of the landscape that have the same uniform type of vegetation. Point quadrat and Disc Pasture Meter surveys are then conducted in each HVU.

4. Point quadrat surveys

Point quadrat surveys are conducted to establish the basal cover and botanical composition of the grass sward. Basal cover is used as an indication of the potential of the grass sward to resist accelerated soil erosion. Sample sites measuring 50m x 100m are located in representative areas of each HVU.

The number of sample sites will depend upon the size and number of HVU's in the survey area.

Experience has shown that a sampling intensity of one sample site per 100ha is a useful guideline for assessing veld condition on a farm scale. A point quadrat survey of 100 random points is conducted to determine the botanical composition of the grass sward. Two transects, 25 meters apart, of 50 points are located down the centre of each half of the sample site and the nearest plant to each point is recorded every 2 meters – see Figure 1. A stick with a sharpened point or a thin metal rod may be used to mark the point from which the measurements are made. The grass species and the distance from the point, measured in centimeters, is recorded at each point. The results are expressed as the percentage relative frequency for each species occurring in the sample site and the mean point to tuft distance representing the basal cover of the grass sward.

Figure 1: Diagram of a Point Quadrat Survey used to record the botanical composition and basal cover of the grass sward

5. The Disc Pasture Meter

The estimation of the standing crop of grass involves the use of the Disc Pasture Meter (DPM) which is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Disc Pasture Meter developed by Bransby & Tainton (1977) used to estimate the standing crop of herbaceous plant material in a grass sward i.e grass fuel load.

The DPM was developed by Bransby & Tainton (1977) and involves relating the settling height of an aluminum disc dropped onto the grass sward to the standing crop of grass holding up the disc, expressed in kilograms per hectare. There is a simple relationship between the settling height and the standing crop of grass based on the fact that the more grass there is the higher off the ground the disc settles. The information derived from the estimation of the standing crop is used for determining what areas should be considered for burning based on the degree to which the grass sward has become moribund and needs to be burnt to restore its palatability, nutritive value and vigour, or for planning grazing strategies.

There are two stages involved in the use of the DPM effectively in the field. The first stage involves the calibration of the DPM i.e. developing the relationship between the settling height of the disc and the standing crop of herbaceous grass material expressed in kg/ha. Trollope & Potgieter (1986) calibrated the DPM for use in the savanna areas of the Kruger National Park in South Africa, and this calibration was subsequently successfully tested in the Eastern Cape of South Africa, the central highlands of Kenya, the Caprivi Strip in Namibia and in the short grass plains in Kansas in the United States of America. The Kruger Park calibration has repeatedly been tested and has been shown to be suitable as the standard calibration for using the DPM in African grasslands and savannas for estimating the standing crop of grass present in a study area.

Determining the mean settling height of the Disc Pasture Meter

The DPM comprises a central rod graduated at one cm intervals and an aluminum disc attached to an aluminum sleeve, which fits over the central rod. The combined mass of the disc and the sleeve is 1.5kg and the diameter of the disc is 45.7cm. The settling height of the disc is recorded by raising the disc to a height of 60cm above the soil surface and dropping it onto the grass sward. The settling height is recorded in centimeters to one decimal place. Care must be taken to avoid placing the central rod in holes, depressions and on hummocks or small shrubs to minimise under- and over- estimations of the mean settling height. In sandy areas the central rod tends to sink into the sand causing over-readings of the settling height. This problem was minimised by fixing a thin, round disc of metal onto the base of the central rod thereby reducing the extent to which the rod sinks into the sand. It is important to keep the central rod in a vertical position, 90 degrees to the perpendicular, when reading the disc height. The table relating mean disc height to standing crop of grass is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Calibration of the DPM for use in African Grasslands and Savannas i.e.

$$Y = -3019 + (2260 \text{ Sqrt.}x)$$

Where Y = Standing crop of grass - kg/ha;

x = Mean disc height - cm;

Sqrt. = Square root transformation.

x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y
2.0	177	6.0	2517	10.0	4128	14.0	5437	18.0	6569	22.0	7581	26.0	8505		
2.1	256	6.1	2563	10.1	4163	14.1	5467	18.1	6596	22.1	7605	26.1	8527		
2.2	333	6.2	2608	10.2	4199	14.2	5497	18.2	6622	22.2	7629	26.2	8549		
2.3	408	6.3	2654	10.3	4234	14.3	5527	18.3	6649	22.3	7653	26.3	8571		
2.4	482	6.4	2698	10.4	4269	14.4	5557	18.4	6675	22.4	7677	26.4	8593		
2.5	554	6.5	2743	10.5	4304	14.5	5587	18.5	6702	22.5	7701	26.5	8615		
2.6	625	6.6	2787	10.6	4339	14.6	5616	18.6	6728	22.6	7725	26.6	8637		
2.7	695	6.7	2831	10.7	4374	14.7	5646	18.7	6754	22.7	7749	26.7	8659		
2.8	763	6.8	2874	10.8	4408	14.8	5675	18.8	6780	22.8	7772	26.8	8681		
2.9	830	6.9	2918	10.9	4442	14.9	5705	18.9	6806	22.9	7796	26.9	8703		
3.0	895	7.0	2960	11.0	4477	15.0	5734	19.0	6832	23.0	7820	27.0	8724		
3.1	960	7.1	3003	11.1	4511	15.1	5763	19.1	6858	23.1	7843	27.1	8746		
3.2	1024	7.2	3045	11.2	4544	15.2	5792	19.2	6884	23.2	7867	27.2	8768		
3.3	1086	7.3	3087	11.3	4578	15.3	5821	19.3	6910	23.3	7890	27.3	8789		
3.4	1148	7.4	3129	11.4	4612	15.4	5850	19.4	6935	23.4	7913	27.4	8811		
3.5	1209	7.5	3170	11.5	4645	15.5	5879	19.5	6961	23.5	7937	27.5	8833		
3.6	1269	7.6	3211	11.6	4678	15.6	5907	19.6	6986	23.6	7960	27.6	8854		
3.7	1328	7.7	3252	11.7	4711	15.7	5936	19.7	7012	23.7	7983	27.7	8876		

x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y	x	Y
3.8	1387	7.8	3293	11.8	4744	15.8	5964	19.8	7037	23.8	8006	27.8	8897	30.0	9360
3.9	1444	7.9	3333	11.9	4777	15.9	5993	19.9	7063	23.9	8030	27.9	8918	30.1	9380
4.0	1501	8.0	3373	12.0	4810	16.0	6021	20.0	7088	24.0	8053	28.0	8940	30.2	9401
4.1	1557	8.1	3413	12.1	4842	16.1	6049	20.1	7113	24.1	8076	28.1	8961	30.3	9421
4.2	1613	8.2	3453	12.2	4875	16.2	6077	20.2	7138	24.2	8099	28.2	8982	30.4	9442
4.3	1667	8.3	3492	12.3	4907	16.3	6105	20.3	7164	24.3	8122	28.3	9004	30.5	9462
4.4	1722	8.4	3531	12.4	4939	16.4	6133	20.4	7189	24.4	8145	28.4	9025	30.6	9483
4.5	1775	8.5	3570	12.5	4971	16.5	6161	20.5	7214	24.5	8167	28.5	9046	30.7	9503
4.6	1828	8.6	3609	12.6	5003	16.6	6189	20.6	7239	24.6	8190	28.6	9067	30.8	9523
4.7	1881	8.7	3647	12.7	5035	16.7	6217	20.7	7263	24.7	8213	28.7	9088	30.9	9544
4.8	1932	8.8	3685	12.8	5067	16.8	6244	20.8	7288	24.8	8236	28.8	9109	31.0	9564
4.9	1984	8.9	3723	12.9	5098	16.9	6272	20.9	7313	24.9	8258	28.9	9130	31.1	9584
5.0	2035	9.0	3761	13.0	5130	17.0	6299	21.0	7338	25.0	8281	29.0	9151	31.2	9605
5.1	2085	9.1	3799	13.1	5161	17.1	6327	21.1	7362	25.1	8304	29.1	9172	31.3	9625
5.2	2135	9.2	3836	13.2	5192	17.2	6354	21.2	7387	25.2	8326	29.2	9193	31.4	9645
5.3	2184	9.3	3873	13.3	5223	17.3	6381	21.3	7411	25.3	8349	29.3	9214	31.5	9665
5.4	2233	9.4	3910	13.4	5254	17.4	6408	21.4	7436	25.4	8371	29.4	9235	31.6	9685
5.5	2281	9.5	3947	13.5	5285	17.5	6435	21.5	7460	25.5	8393	29.5	9256		
5.6	2329	9.6	3983	13.6	5315	17.6	6462	21.6	7485	25.6	8416	29.6	9277		
5.7	2377	9.7	4020	13.7	5346	17.7	6489	21.7	7509	25.7	8438	29.7	9297		
5.8	2424	9.8	4056	13.8	5377	17.8	6516	21.8	7533	25.8	8460	29.8	9318		
5.9	2471	9.9	4092	13.9	5407	17.9	6543	21.9	7557	25.9	8483	29.9	9339		

NOTE: i) The mean disc height is based on 100 readings;

ii) This calibration was developed by Trollope & Potgieter (1986) - *Estimating Grass Fuel Loads with A Disc*

Pasture Meter In The Kruger National Park - J.Grassl. Soc. Sth. Afr. (1986) 3,4:148 -152.

6. Key Grass Species Assessment Form

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland**MPUMALANGA PROVINCE**

Sample Site: GPS: S - Date:

Soil Type: E - RECORDER:.....

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Mononcybium ceresiforme</i>		5		4	
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>		4		3	
DECREASER TOTAL			*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i>		2		4	
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>		-3		-4	
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>		3		3	
INCREASER I TOTAL			*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>		0		1	
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>		1		3	
	<i>Eragrostis plana</i>		-2		-2	
	<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i>		-12		-10	
	FORBS		-2		-2	
	BARE GROUND		-12		-10	
INCREASER II TOTAL			*****		*****	
OTHERS			CONSTANT	366	CONSTANT	554
TOTAL		100.0	TOTAL		TOTAL	
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 727x100% =						

CONCLUSIONS (tick appropriate block)							
1) <u>VELD CONDITION</u>				4) <u>ROTATIONAL GRAZING</u>	5) <u>ROTATIONAL RESTING</u>		
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding?		
>500	Very High			HPG?	Vigour?		
401 - 500	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?		
301 - 400	Medium			<u>REASON:</u>	<u>REASON:</u>		
200 - 300	Low						
<200	Very Low						
2) <u>MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY</u>				6) <u>LIVESTOCK RATIO</u>			
GC = $365/(-31.159 + (1.433 \times VCS\%)) + ((\text{Rainfall} - 419.7) \times 0.231)$ GC = HA/AU				7) <u>TREND</u>			
				Recommended = 1AU: 6 SSU	CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION
Where: (Danckwerts 1981) GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit; VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %; Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.				Current =AU:SSU	Decreaser	Correctly stocked	
					Increaser I		Under stocked
					Increaser II		Over Stocked
					Increaser II	Selectively Grazed	
				COMMENT:			
3) <u>STOCKING RATE</u>							
Predicted =ha/AU							
Current =ha/AU							

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	<3cm	3-5cm	>5cm
Distance – cm =			
Grass Standing Crop	LOW		HIGH
	>1500kg/ha		<1500kg/ha
kg/ha =			
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			

9) <u>VELD BURNING</u>			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER			
INCREASER I			
INCREASER II			
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha =			
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			

DECREASER SPECIES – grass species which decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES – grass species which increase with under or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES – grass species which increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; **Email:** winfire@procomp.co.za.

7. Glossary & Interpretation of Veld Condition Surveys

i) VELD CONDITION

Veld Condition refers to the condition of the vegetation in relation to some functional characteristic (Trollope *et al*, 1990). In livestock production systems based on grassland vegetation the three most important functional characteristics are the forage and fuel production potential of the grass sward and its resistance to accelerated soil erosion.

ii) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (Vegetation Dependent)

Productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU or AU/ha. Mean Grazing Capacity is estimated taking into account the Veld Condition Score (VCS) and the previous 12 months rainfall using the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) viz.

$$\text{GRAZING CAPACITY} = 365 / (-31.159 + (1.433 * \text{VCS } \%) + ((\text{Rainfall mm} - 419.7) \times 0.231))$$

WHERE:

GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares per Animal Unit – HA/AU;

VCS % = Veld Condition Score expressed as a percentage;

Rainfall mm = Previous 12 months rainfall expressed in millimetres

The Veld Condition Score is estimated using the formula:

$$\text{VCS } \% = (\text{Sample Forage Score} / \text{Benchmark Forage Score}) \times 100$$

REFERENCE:

Danckwerts, J.E., 1981. *A technique to assess the grazing capacity of sweetveld with particular reference to the False Thornveld areas of the Ciskei*. MSc Thesis, Dept. Pasture Science, Univ. Natal, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa: 1-245.

iii) STOCKING RATE (Operator Dependent)

Stocking Rate refers to the area of land in the system of management which the operator has allocated to each animal unit in the system (Booyesen, 1967). Stocking rate has a major influence on animal performance, economic return to the farmer and the long term condition of the veld and is the most important veld management practice.

GUIDELINES: FOR STOCKING RATE:

The formulation of stocking rates for grazing animals (cattle and sheep) is based on the mean grazing capacity of the veld. This is estimated by using the veld conditions score (VCS) in the formula presented by Trollope and Willis (1984) which describes the relationship between VCS and the mean grazing capacity.

$$GC = \frac{100 \times GC.BM}{VCS}$$

where:

GC = mean grazing capacity;

GC.BM = mean grazing capacity of the benchmark;

VCS = veld condition score

iv) ROTATIONAL GRAZING

Rotational grazing is the successive occupation of camps by livestock during the year so that not all the veld is grazed simultaneously (Tainton, 1981). There are two forms of rotational grazing:

- High Production Grazing (HPG) – the occupation of a camp by grazing animals until **all the acceptable and desirable Decreaser grass species** have been grazed to a stage that will ensure rapid regrowth and a high production of forage;
- High Utilization Grazing (HUG) – the occupation of a camp by grazing animals until **all the grass species** have been heavily grazed.

The use of these different forms of rotational grazing depends upon the condition of the veld and specifically the dominance of the different categories of grass species i.e. decreaser and increaser species. Of course besides applying the correct form of rotational grazing appropriate adjustment must also be made to the stocking rate.

GUIDELINES FOR ROTATIONAL GRAZING:

- a) If grass sward is dominated by |Increaser | and || species this indicates selective grazing and requires application of HUG to reduce |Increaser | species and promote Decreaser species;
- b) If grass sward dominated by |Increaser | species this indicates undergrazing and requires application of HUG to reduce |Increaser | species and promote Decreaser species;
- c) If grass sward dominated by |Increaser || species this indicates overgrazing and requires application of HPG to reduce |Increaser || species and promote Decreaser species;
- d) If grass sward dominated by Decreaser species this indicates optimum grazing and requires application of HPG and HUG to maintain Decreaser species and prevent development of |Increaser | and || species.

Decreaser species dominated veld

This is veld that is in ideal condition for livestock production. This veld condition can be maintained by applying HGP which will ensure the high production of good quality forage and excellent animal performance. This is because the preferred grass species are grazed according to their physiological requirements and the livestock allowed selecting a superior diet. However, it is necessary to periodically apply HUG to maintain the veld at the decreaser stage in the grassland succession and prevent it from developing to the |Increaser | stage. In the sour and mixed veld areas this should be done once a year and in the sweetveld areas once every three years.

|Increaser | species dominated veld

This is veld that has either been understocked or selectively grazed. Both these practices allow the grassland succession to progress from the sub-climax decrease stage to the higher increaser | stage. In order to reverse the succession to the more desirable decreaser stage it is necessary to apply HUG. This can be combined with veld burning or the feeding of nitrogen/protein licks so as to minimise the negative aspects of this form of rotational grazing on animal performance.

Increaser II species dominated veld

This is veld that has been overstocked and is being overgrazed and ecologically constitutes a reversal in the grassland succession from the decreaser stage to the lower pioneer increaser II stage. This can be reversed by applying HPG where the less abundant but more competitive decreaser species will be favoured and encouraged to increase and dominate the sward. This treatment will also ensure good animal performance.

Increaser I and II species dominated veld

This type of veld develops in situations where there are a few large camps in the grazing system and either continuous grazing or a very low form of rotational grazing is applied. Both result in selective grazing which encourages increaser I species. However, these two forms of grazing also result in the overgrazing of the decreaser species in the sward because of the extended grazing periods. This allows the increaser II species to dominate in the spaces between the less acceptable and tufted increaser I species.

The condition of this type of veld can be improved by subdividing the large camps into a multi-camp system and applying a combination of HUG and HPG. The HUG can be combined with either veld burning or the feeding of nitrogen / protein licks as described earlier. However, this treatment should only be applied for a maximum period of two growing seasons after which HPG is used to encourage the decreaser species. The HUG treatment will firstly severely defoliate the increaser I species, which are less tolerant to grazing, but the subsequent application of HPG will then encourage and improve the vigour of the decreaser species when it is applied.

v) ROTATIONAL RESTING

Rotational resting of the grass sward is the successive withdrawal of veld from grazing on a rotational basis for specific purposes. The principle reasons for resting veld are seeding, restoration of vigour and providing a fodder reserve for periods of scarcity. Besides stocking rate, rotational resting is one of the most important and essential veld management practices.

GUIDELINES FOR ROTATIONAL RESTING

- i) If grass sward dominated by Increaser I and/or II species apply seeding rest to promote Decreaser species i.e. Jan/Jan rest to promote *Themeda triandra* (rooigras) if potential dominant species;
- ii) If grass sward dominated by Decreaser species apply a vigour and fodder reserve rest to promote productivity and provide forage for periods of scarcity i.e. July/July rest to allow full growing

seasons growth to promote grass vigour and accumulation and provision of a fodder reserve at the end of winter;

- iii) General rule – Sourveld areas – rest $\frac{1}{4}$ of grazing area annually; Sweetveld areas – rest $\frac{1}{3}$ of grazing area annually.

A seeding rest is applied when the decreaser species have declined in the grass sward. It is, therefore, appropriate when either increaser I or II species are dominant but in practice is more important in veld that has been overstocked where there is a serious lack of decrease grass species and the basal cover of the sward is very poor. Generally the most widely applicable rest period to apply for veld in this condition is from January to January because it maximises the production of seed by *Themeda triandra* (red grass) the most important and widely distributed decreaser species in the veld.

Resting the veld to restore plant vigour is necessary under all veld conditions and is aimed at the decreaser species. In the sweetveld areas this necessitates resting the veld for a full year so that the grass plants can grow to maturity at which stage they are still valuable forage for livestock. In mixed and sourveld areas a shorter rest comprising the late summer and autumn period (January - April) is adequate for this purpose and reduces the extent to which the grass becomes mature and unacceptable to livestock.

A fodder reserve rest is necessary under all veld conditions but enjoys priority when the veld is in excellent condition and seed production is not important. It is intended to provide a fodder reserve for that time of the year when there is the greatest likelihood of a deficiency. In the summer rainfall area of southern Africa this is during late winter/early spring (August/September). In the sweetveld areas the most appropriate rest period for this purpose is from July to July while in the mixed and sourveld areas from January to July. When applying these rests it is important to use HUG beforehand so as to ensure that only new nutritious forage is produced during the rest period.

vi) LIVESTOCK RATIOS

Livestock ratios refer to the ratio of bulk grazers to concentrate grazers. The selective grazing habit of domestic livestock is related to the grazing sequence in which these different classes of animals utilize the veld. Normally heavy bulk grazers (cattle) precede light concentrate grazers (sheep) thus preparing the pasture for use by the animals which follow.

GUIDELINES FOR LIVESTOCK RATIOS

- i) Sourveld areas - Ratio of cattle to sheep should not exceed 1 AU to 6 SSU (Danckwerts, 1989);
- ii) Sweetveld areas - Ratio of cattle to sheep should not exceed 1 AU to 3 SSU because in arid areas the veld is more susceptible to selective grazing.

vii) TREND

Trends in the condition of the veld are indicated by the percentage Decreaser and/or Increaser grass species present in the grass sward. Decreaser dominant veld indicates correct stocking rates, Increaser I dominated veld indicates under stocking whereas Increaser II dominated veld indicates over stocking or Increaser I and II dominated veld indicates selectively grazed veld. Negative trends can be reversed either by resting, changing the grazing management and/or by burning.

viii) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL

The Soil Erosion Potential is the potential of the veld to resist soil erosion and is influenced by the Basal Cover represented by the Point to Tuft Distance (measured in cm) and the Standing Crop of Grass (kg/ha) estimated with a Disc Pasture Meter.

ix) VELD BURNING

Veld burning is an important and often essential management practice in livestock production systems, particularly in sourveld areas. There are two primary and valid reasons for burning veld:

- i) Remove moribund and/or unacceptable grass material;
- ii) Eradicate and/or prevent the encroachment of undesirable plants.

Burning is ecologically permissible if the veld is dominated by Decreaser and/or Increaser I grass species. Burning is not recommended if Increaser II grass species are dominant as the veld should be given an opportunity to progress to a higher stage of plant succession i.e. to improve from pioneer increaser II grass species to the more productive and palatable Decreaser species stage. Post-fire grazing management is very important as it has the greatest positive or negative effect on veld condition.